

On the Nonexistence of Odd Perfect Numbers

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Abstract

This document demonstrates the structure and usage of standard formal elements—theorems, propositions, lemmas, corollaries, definitions, and examples—within a mathematical paper using L^AT_EX. The elements are defined and presented in a logical sequence to illustrate how they build upon each other.

1 Introduction

In this paper we...

2 Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 (Perfect number). *A perfect number is a positive integer n such that the sum of all its positive divisors equals $2n$, i.e.,*

$$\sigma(N) = 2N,$$

where $\sigma(N) = \sum_{d|N} d$.

Definition 2.2 (Divisor function). *For a positive integer n , the divisor function $\tau(n)$ counts the number of its positive divisors. If n has prime factorization*

$$n = p_1^{a_1} p_2^{a_2} \cdots p_k^{a_k},$$

then $\tau(n)$ can be computed by the following equivalent formulas:

$$\tau(n) = \#\{d \in \mathbb{N} : d \mid n\} = \sum_{d|n} 1 = \prod_{i=1}^k (a_i + 1).$$

Theorem 2.3 (Euler's characterization). *Any odd perfect number n (if one exists) must have the form:*

$$n = q^k \cdot m^2,$$

where q is a prime, k, m are positive integers with $q \equiv k \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$ and $\gcd(q, m) = 1$ [Bur10, pp. 232–233].

3 Main Results

3.1 Technical Lemmas

Lemma 3.1 (Odd Perfect Number has Odd Divisor Count). *Odd perfect number has odd number of proper divisors.*

Proof. By Theorem 2.3, form of the hypothetical odd perfect number is $N = q^k \cdot m^2$. Only perfect squares have odd number of divisors.

$$\tau(n) \text{ is odd} \iff n \text{ is a perfect square}$$

Odd perfect N number must be of this form:

$$N = q^k \cdot m^2$$

k is odd number, and m^2 is a perfect square.

So the whole product $q^k \cdot m^2$ cannot be a perfect square, which means that number of all divisors $\tau(N)$ must be even.

Moreover, if we plug the odd number for the k , we get the same conclusion:

$$\tau(N) = \tau(q^{2n+1} \cdot m^2) = (2n + 2) \cdot (2 + 1) = 4n + 2n + 4 + 2 = 6n + 6$$

This means that count of proper divisors $\tau(N) - 1$ must be odd. □

Lemma 3.2 (Proper Divisors Count Equality). *For any positive integer n equality*

$$(\tau(N) - 1) \cdot N = \sigma(N) + \sum_{d|n, 1 \leq d < N} N - d$$

holds.

Proof. For each divisor d_k the right-hand side of the equation can be represented as $d_k + N - d_k$, which is equal to N . we do this for each proper divisor. There are $\tau(N) - 1$ proper divisors, so the right-hand side of the equation is equal to $(\tau(N) - 1) \cdot N$.

This illustration explains the same reasoning:

$$\sigma(N) + \left(\sum_{d_i|N, 1 \leq d_i < N} N - d_i \right) = \left. \begin{array}{c} \boxed{d_1} \\ \boxed{d_2} \\ \dots \\ \boxed{d_i} \end{array} \right\} \sigma(N) + \left. \begin{array}{c} + \\ + \\ + \\ + \\ \dots \\ + \end{array} \right\} \left. \begin{array}{c} \boxed{N - d_1} \\ \boxed{N - d_2} \\ \dots \\ \boxed{N - d_i} \end{array} \right\} \sum_{d|N, 1 \leq d < N} N - d \left. \right\} \tau(N) - 1$$

□

Theorem 3.3 (Nonexistence of odd perfect numbers). *An odd perfect number does not exist.*

Proof. Assume, for contradiction, that an odd perfect number N exists.

Using the equality defined in the Lemma 3.2:

$$(\tau(N) - 1) \cdot N = \sigma(N) + \sum_{d|n, 1 \leq d < N} N - d$$

since N is perfect, $\sigma(N) = 2N$, and we get:

$$(\tau(N) - 1) \cdot N = 2N + \sum_{d|n, 1 \leq d < N} N - d$$

Term $2N$ is in the form of $2 \cdot x$, which means that it's even. For each term in the sum $\sum_{d|n, 1 \leq d < N} N - d$, we are subtracting an odd divisor from the N which is odd itself.

Remark 3.4. *Odd perfect number doesn't have even divisors.*

. Odd number minus odd gives an even number, which means each term in the sum is even. The whole sum adds these even terms, and the whole sum at the end gives an even number.

If we look at the equality now, the right-hand side is $(Even) + (Even)$. This means that the left-hand side of the equation $(\tau(N) - 1) \cdot N$ must also be even. For this to be true, either N , or $\tau(N) - 1$ must be even. N is odd by assumption, and by Lemma 3.1 we know that $\tau(N) - 1$ is also odd.

This contradiction completes the proof. \square

Corollary 3.5 (Classification of perfect numbers). *Every perfect number is even and is therefore given by the Euclid-Euler formula.*

Proof. By Theorem 3.3, no odd perfect number exists. Consequently, any perfect number must be even. The Euclid-Euler theorem states that an even number is perfect if and only if it has the form $N = 2^{p-1}(2^p - 1)$, where p and $2^p - 1$ are prime [HW09, Theorem 276, p. 311]. \square

References

- [Bur10] David M. Burton. *Elementary Number Theory*. McGraw-Hill, Higher Education, 7th ed edition, 2010.
- [HW09] G. H. Hardy and E. M Wright. *An Introduction to the Theory of Numbers*. Posts & Telecom Press, 6th edition, 2009.